

1 **ALOX15B activation in ulcerative colitis.**

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6 Lipid mediators are inflammatory factors that include leukotrienes and prostaglandins and are
7 derived from the eicosanoid arachidonic acid. We describe here transcriptional activation and differential
8 expression of an enzyme functioning in the arachidonic acid biosynthetic pathway, arachidonate
9 15-lipoxygenase, type B (*ALOX15b*) in the blood of humans with active ulcerative colitis. In a cohort of
10 children and young adults with ulcerative colitis, ALOX15B was transcriptionally active in mucosal tissue of
11 the colon. Functionally, ALOX15b is transcriptionally co-regulated with the interleukins IL28a and IL-37, a
12 cytokine whose genetic deficiency results in very early onset inflammatory bowel disease (ulcerative
13 colitis). These data support a role for hematopoietic-derived ALOX15B activity in tissues in propagating
14 rather than countering inflammation.
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Results

We used published whole transcriptome data (1, 2) from patient tissues during inactive and active disease to identify novel therapeutic targets in the hematopoietic tissues of patients with ulcerative colitis, one of two major inflammatory bowel diseases, and to support basic description of transcriptional activity most closely associated with disease state and activity level of disease in the blood.

Figure 1: ALOX15B is transcriptionally activated in the blood of humans with ulcerative colitis during periods of active disease.

GSE186507

n=207 whole blood, control

n=13 whole blood, UC, active disease, severe endoscopic severity

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
247	2.31e-02	0.2624	-2.2722245	-0.59625592	6.45	ALOX15B	5166/21274	75.7

Figure 2: ALOX15B is a part of the M2 macrophage gene signature.

GSE243175

PBMC were matured and differentiated in M-CSF for 5 days and IL-4 for 2 days to polarize to the M2 lineage.

n=2 monocytes from PBMC (human)

n=2 M2 macrophages (differentiated in M-CSF and IL4)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
247	1.40E-20	0.531	-9.30067	-4.9375206	1095.24	ALOX15B	439/17645	97.5

Figure 3: In the monocytes of humans with Crohn's Disease, ALOX15B is silenced, but ALOX5 is activated.

GSE69446

n=2 monocytes (human; control)

n=3 monocytes (human; Crohn's Disease; mutant for *NOD2*)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
247	1.56E-11	0.237	6.742507	1.5964117	256.49	ALOX15B	26/17330	99.8
240	1.08E-03	0.258	-3.268999	-0.8445326	9077.92	ALOX5	505/17330	97.1

Figure 4: ALOX15b is over-expressed and differentially expressed in the colons of children with ulcerative colitis.

GSE126124

n=19 colon (healthy; control)

n=4 colon (ulcerative colitis; age 8-16)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8004784	4.82e-02	-2.07761135	-3.99341	-0.22788553	ALOX15B	6080/33297	81.7

Figure 5: ALOX15b expression is associated with transcription of IL-37, a gene whose mutation is found in very early onset IBD.

Discussion

We have identified activation of inflammatory factor ALOX15B in the blood of humans with the inflammatory bowel disease ulcerative colitis. In the monocytes of humans with the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease, ALOX5 was activated rather than ALOX15B. Studies evaluating ALOX15/ALOX15b function in colitis have contrarily reported an anti- rather than pro-inflammatory role for ALOX15b but were restricted to study of mucosal tissues, not the blood (5-9). We found that ALOX15B was transcribed in a network with IL-37, a gene with innate immune functions whose expression is associated with very early onset IBD (10-13), as well as IL-28A. Our analysis of transcriptional changes associated with disease and disease activity in the hematopoietic system of humans with ulcerative colitis will provide an enhanced understanding of cellular activity and transcriptional dynamics that describe disease state and disease activation level/status resulting in significant morbidity. Elucidation of inflammatory and metabolic factors that originate from hematopoietic tissues but result in tissue damage and pathology in the gastrointestinal tract is critical for therapeutic management and early disease prevention.

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